

Binomial Theorem on the Coefficients for Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper presents a binomial and factorial theorem on the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-10]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-10] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem 2.1: $\frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = V_n^r$, where $n, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$.

Proof. $\binom{n+r}{n} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!(n+r-n)!} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \cdots (n+r)}{r!} = V_n^r$.

Hence, theorem is proved.

Theorem 2.2: $\frac{((p+1)n)!}{(pn)!(n)!} = (p+1) \frac{((p+1)n-1)!}{n!(n-1)!}$, $(p \geq 1; n \geq 0 \& p, n \in N)$.

Proof. Let us use the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series

$$\begin{aligned} V_{pn}^n &= \frac{(pn+1)(pn+2)(pn+3)\cdots(pn+n-1)(pn+n)}{(n)!} \\ &= \frac{(pn+1)(pn+2)(pn+3)\cdots(pn+n-1)((p+1)n)}{(n-1)!n} \\ &= \frac{(p+1)(pn+1)(pn+2)(pn+3)\cdots(pn+n-1)}{(n-1)!} = (p+1)V_{pn}^{n-1}. \end{aligned}$$

By applying Theorem 2.1 to the equation $V_{pn}^n = (p+1)V_{pn}^{n-1}$, we get

$$\frac{(pn+n)}{(pn)!n!} = (p+1) \frac{(pn+n-1)}{(pn)!(n-1)!} \Rightarrow \frac{((p+1)n)!}{(pn)!(n)!} = (p+1) \frac{((p+1)n-1)!}{n!(n-1)!}.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

Conclusion

In this article, a binomial and factorial theorem was built using the binomial theorem on the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

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